

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 63.2969 Max: 63.4934	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1176 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Natural <input type="checkbox"/> Anthropic		Gabii Project
-------------	--------------	-----------	--------	---	--	--	---------------

In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 608-611	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #:
--	--	--	--

DEFINITION layer between 1163 and 1187	Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1016	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
---	--	---------------------------------------	---

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition
---	---

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX clay 10% silt 90% sand ___%
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery R <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)
			Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft
			Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)		Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Southern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Western Limit	<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	cut by 1152
Eastern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1016	Covers: 1189
Is cut by: 1152	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS
- excavated with shallow pick axing

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: West of center in Area B
Shape: rectangular oriented W-E

For layers complete this section:
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): slopes downwards towards the E
no visible inclusions on surface
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope)
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): consistently thin
Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commigled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:
Cut edges: rounded straight
Cut sides: straight concave convex sloping
Cut bottom: flat concave irregular
How is cut top edge? sharp rounded
How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded
Observations:

 orthogonal blocks

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

- layer cut on the W side by 1152 → the cut from
 grave # 23 ("Fran")
 - thin, silty post-abandonment layer between wall
 1163 and 1187

SOIL SAMPLING: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No Total volume of layer (buckets): Sample quantity (buckets): Sample fraction (%):	NON SOIL SAMPLES: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.): Size:	SIEVING: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No Total volume of layer (buckets): Sample quantity (buckets): Sample fraction (%):